

Assessment of Background Radiation Around Telecommunication Masts of the Major Network Service Providers in Kaduna South, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This work assessed the electromagnetic radiation from telecommunication masts of major service providers (AIRTEL, ETISALAT, GLO, and MTN) around residential areas in Kaduna South, Nigeria. The Radio Frequency Electromagnetic Force (RF EMF) strength meter of serial number (480836) and a measuring tape were used to obtain readings away from the masts. The electric field strengths E, magnetic field strengths H, and power densities were measured at 0 m, 100 m, 200 m, 300 m, 400 m, and 500 m away from the mast base in V/m, A/m, and W/m², respectively. The power densities measured were: 0.000091 W/m² for Airtel, 0.000195 W/m² for Etisalat, 0.000488 W/m² for GLO, and 0.421352 W/m²

for MTN. These readings were compared with the standard value (4.5 W/m²) recommended by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) and the 6.05 W/m² recommended by the Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers (IEEE) for exposure limits of radio frequency waves and the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) and were discovered to be below the recommended values. The radiological health effects, absorbed radiation dose rates, the annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE), and the excess lifetime cancer risks (ELCR) were evaluated. The values of absorbed dose rates were 0.000091 Gys⁻¹ for Airtel, 0.000195333 Gys⁻¹ for Etisalat, 0.000488333 Gys⁻¹ for GLO, and 0.421352 Gys⁻¹ for MTN, which were observed to be far lower than the world permissible value of 0.02472 Gys⁻¹, except that of MTN, which is higher than the permissible value. However, the estimated annual effective dose equivalents (AEDE) were found to be higher than the ICNIRP permissible limits of 1.00 mSvy⁻¹ for the public, which implies that the base stations do pose radiological risks in the long term. Also, the excess lifetime cancer risk for the stations' users was all above the 0.29 × 10⁻³ per Sievert world recommended value by the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiations, UNSCEAR (2018), and Audu *et al.*, (2019). This, therefore, suggests there is a high probability of the base station workers and residents within 500 m of the base mast to develop radiation-related illnesses over a long time. Regular radiological monitoring of all the base stations is recommended.

Keywords: Radiation, Absorption rate, Base station, Health effects.

Introduction

Across the globe, a growing number of various bands of networks—2G, 3G, 4G, as well as 5G—are being installed. Later, it generated considerable misunderstanding on social media platforms around the world, including in Nigeria, when it was argued that the 5G network has more advantages than disadvantages. In contrast with certain individuals who contend that 5G simply emits non-ionizing radiation in the range of 2G, 3G, and 4G networks, which are deemed to pose no reported health risks, there are groups of people who believe that the 5G network emits a significant amount of radiation and, as a result, believe that it has health implications. The Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), in a release dated April 5, 2020, explained that the 5G network had no effects on health in order to assuage the worry the 5G network had caused in Nigeria (NCC, 2020).

Mobile phone base stations emit radiation that is inhaled by people. Mobile phones use radio waves from an installed telecommunications network. Given the fact that the mobile phone and its base station function are two-way radios, they emit radiofrequency (RF) radiation in order to communicate, which exposes any surrounding individuals to RF radiation. The question of whether there are any implications for human health has naturally arisen as a result of the widespread usage of mobile phones and the ongoing expanding of base stations (Kun-Hoong, 2003). In recent decades, RF radiation from mobile phones and their base stations has been the subject of discussions about potential health dangers that have alarmed both the general public and scientists.

Initially, the international scientific community believed that the power from these base station antennas was quite small to cause health hazards, provided people were kept away from direct contact with the antennas (Kwan-Hoong, 2003). Also, results of expert studies by the World Health Organization (WHO), the UK Advisory Group on Non-Ionizing Radiation (AGNIR), and the Scientific Committee on Emerging and Newly Identified Health Risks (SCENIHR) all

show that there is no evidence of adverse health effects of radiation exposure from base stations, provided it remains below the levels set by current standards (Handell, 2017).

However, recently released research has demonstrated that radiation from base stations and mobile phones poses a risk to both human health and the environment. For instance, the majority of laboratory investigations, according to Singh et al. (2018), have shown a direct link between exposure to RF radiation and adverse biological effects. According to several *in vitro* studies, RF radiation causes DNA or chromosomal damage as well as a number of different cancers (Singh et al., 2018). By using a descriptive cross-sectional survey, Akintonwa et al. (2009) assessed the health risks of non-ionizing radiation from telecommunication masts on the exposed community and found that about 62% of the people were affected health-wise by exposure to mast radiation reducing these risks would significantly improve the health of the population. According to technical reports on toxicology and carcinogenesis studies in rats exposed to whole-body radiofrequency radiation at 900 MHz and in mice exposed to whole-body radiofrequency radiation at 1,900 MHz. it was revealed that there is strong evidence that RF radiation is a human carcinogen, causing glioma and vestibular schwannoma (acoustic neuroma), by Handell et al. 2019. Additionally, there is some evidence of an elevated risk of thyroid cancer and unmistakable proof that RF radiation is a multi-site carcinogen. After analyzing MPs usage and adolescent understanding of health risks, Handell et al. (2019) and Ferdous (2017) indicated that 70% of teenagers who use MPs in Sylhet City are dealing with various health issues. Evidence on the relationship between non-ionizing radiation and increasing the level of radiation exposure was studied by Santini et al., (2002). They found more significant symptoms of health effects within a radius of 300 m from the mobile phone base stations: irritability, depression, memory loss, dizziness, decreased libido, headache, sleep disorders, malaise (200 m), and tiredness (300 m). Similarly, Oberfeld et al., (2010) found that persons living close to base

stations reported more symptoms of irritability, fatigue, headache, nausea, memory loss, visual disturbances, dizziness, and cardiovascular problems, directly proportional to their exposure to microwaves.

According to Osaretin, it has become part of the environment to see telecommunication masts at different locations around the country. This accounts for the preponderance of the mast in the areas requisite for human habitation. Also, the increasing rate of users of the services providers of MTN, AIRTEL, ETISALAT, and GLO, has led to a corresponding increase in the installations of the telecommunication masts of these service providers, which has therefore mandated the assessment of the radiation emitted from these masts to ascertain the health effects as well as the risks they pose to man and his environment. This study is aimed at assessing the effect of radiation emitting from the telecommunication masts of the major service providers (MTN, AIRTEL, ETISALAT, and GLO) in Kaduna South, Nigeria, estimating the health implications on the populace, and orienting researchers, the general public, students, and the government about the health implications of the radiation emitted from telecommunication masts.

Methodology

The methodology deployed here includes equipment calibration and data measurement from the surveyed masts of the GSM service providers. The primary data obtained using the RF EMF Strength meter and secondary data from the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP), the Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers (IEEE), and the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) were used.

Materials

The instruments used for this study were a 3.5 GHz RF EMF strength meter (Radio Frequency Electromagnetic Field Strength Meter) model 480836 and a measuring tape.

Equipment Calibration

The RF EMF strength meter is a broadband isotropic instrument. This meter is a broadband device for monitoring high-frequency radiation in the specific ranges of 900 MHz, 1800 MHz, and 2.7 GHz. Other measurements can be made, for reference purposes only, using the entire range of 50 MHz to 3.5 GHz. The non-directional electric field's high sensitivity also allows measurements of electric field strength in TEM cells and absorber rooms. The unit of measurement and the measurement types are expressed in units of electrical and magnetic field strength as well as power density. At high frequencies, the power density is of particular significance. It provides a measure of the power absorbed by a person exposed to the field. This power level must be kept as low as possible at high frequencies. The meter can be set to display the instantaneous value, the maximum value measured, or the average value. Instantaneous and maximum value measurements are useful for orientation.

Service Providers Mast Surveyed

Major Nigeria's service providers were considered: Airtel, Etisalat, Glo and MTN. Five base stations each were selected, making a total of twenty base stations surveyed. Each base station carried either three dual-band antennas or six single-band antennas. The antennas are usually arranged into three sectors at 120 degrees apart. The height of the towers ranges from 25 m to 55 m. Some base stations were fenced, while others were not.

Measuring Techniques

Measurements were taken from 0 m to 500 m at 100 m intervals away from the mast. In a fenced station, the base of the fences served as the origin of the measurement. At each point, the values of electric field strength, magnetic field strength, and power density were measured while ensuring the meter was in maximum mode.

Analysis

The mean BIR exposure rates obtained were quantitatively used to assess the radiation health impact on workers within the immediate environment of the stations by performing

several radiological health indices calculations, such as absorbed dose rate, annual effective dose equivalent, and excess lifetime cancer risk, using the necessary relationships given by ConvertWizard.com (2022) and Ezekiel (2017). The power densities were converted to watts per kilogram and then to absorbed dose rates using the relation in equation (1).

$$1 \text{ gray per second [Gy/s]} = 1 \text{ watt per kilogram [W/ kg]} \quad (1)$$

The computed absorbed dose rates were used to calculate the annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE), a radiation protection index that quantifies the whole-body absorbed dose per year (Ogbede, 2018) using equation (2) (UNSCEAR, 2000).

$$\text{AEDE} = \text{ADR (Gy/s)} \times 31,536,6000 \text{ s} \times 0.7 \text{ Sv/Gy} \times 0.2 \quad (2)$$

ADR equals the absorbed dose rate in Gy/s, 31,536,000 equals the total seconds in a year, and 0.7 Sv/Gy equals the dose conversion factor from the absorbed dose in the air to the effective dose using an occupancy factor of 0.2 for outdoor exposure as recommended by the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR).

The excess lifetime cancer risks were evaluated using the annual effective dose values by employing equation (3) (Odoh et al., 2018).

$$\text{ELCR} = \text{AEDE (mSv/y)} \times \text{DL} \times \text{RF} \quad (3)$$

where AEDE is the annual effective dose equivalent, DL is the average duration of life (70 years), and RF is the fatal cancer risk factor per Sievert (Sv⁻¹). For low-dose background radiation, which is considered to produce stochastic effects, International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) 103 uses a fatal cancer risk factor value of 0.05 for public exposure (Paquet *et al.*, 2019).

Results and Discussion

The values for the annual effective dose for all the masts in this study are higher than the ICRP permissible limits of 1.00 mSv⁻¹ for the general public (Parquet *et al.*, 2018). This indicates that the studied masts are not in agreement with the permissible limit. The absorbed dose rates arising from the BIR levels of the masts and the annual effective radiation doses at these rates do constitute an immediate radiological health effect on the mast workers and the general public. The values for the cancer risks obtained in this work are far higher than the average value of 0.29×10^{-3} per Sievert as recommended by UNSCEAR (2018) and Audu *et al.*, (2019). The implication of this is that those who visit the base stations on a daily basis and members of the public who either live or work a few meters away from the stations and end up spending long hours within the stations are likely to develop cancer at ages 65 to 70 years or older in their lifetime. It is therefore recommended that the radiation levels of the masts and, hence, their surroundings be monitored against any further increase.

Table 1. Airtel Mast with ID: 047

Distance (m)	Electric Field Strength (V/m)	Magnetic Field Strength (A/m)	Power Density (W/m ²)
0	0.831200	0.002010	0.000170
100	0.049600	0.000152	0.000096
200	0.028000	0.000085	0.000032
300	0.038900	0.000099	0.000048
400	0.049600	0.000240	0.000152
500	0.046600	0.000008	0.000048
		Average	0.000091

Table 2. Etisalat Mast with ID: 0154

Distance (m)	Electric Field Strength (V/m)	Magnetic Field Strength (A/m)	Power Density (W/m ²)
0	0.403100	0.001149	0.000500
100	0.158240	0.0001368	0.000272
200	0.093760	0.000119	0.000136
300	0.053848	0.000102	0.000072
400	0.051456	0.000159	0.000104
500	0.049032	0.000172	0.000088
		Average	0.000195

Table 3. Glo Mast with ID: KAD 060

Distance(m)	Electric Field Strength (V/m)	Magnetic Field Strength (A/m)	Power Density (W/m ²)
0	0.645000	0.0038000	0.0025000
100	0.031200	0.0002340	0.0000880
200	0.019980	0.0002300	0.0000560
300	0.050456	0.0002000	0.0001260
400	0.042496	0.0001774	0.0000960
500	0.046560	0.0001110	0.0000640
		Average	0.000488

Table 4. MTN mast with ID 0160

Distance (m)	Electric field strength (V/m)	Magnetic Field Strength (A/m)	Power Density (W/m ²)
0	2.127000	0.978000	2.080200
100	0.159920	0.054320	0.108584
200	0.205200	0.000082	0.000208
300	0.246080	0.000980	0.000304
400	0.189200	0.071060	0.168352
500	0.196160	0.069520	0.170464
		Average	0.421352

Table 5: comparison of the result obtained and percentage ratio (PR) of the maximum power density of each service provider with the

standard value given by ICNIRP, FCC, and IEEE

Table 5. Comparison of the Result Obtained

Service Providers Mast	Maximum Power Density (W/M ²)	Standard Limitgiven			PR with ICNIRP (%)	PR with FCC (%)	PR with IEEE (%)
		ICNIRP (W/m ²)	FCC (W/m ²)	IEEE (W/m ²)			
AIRTEL	0.000091	4.50	6.05	6.05	0.002	0.002	0.002
ETISALAT	0.000195	4.50	6.05	6.05	0.004	0.003	0.003
GLOBACOM	0.000488	4.50	6.05	6.05	0.011	0.008	0.008
MTN	0.421352	4.50	6.05	6.05	9.324	6.964	6.964

Table 6. A Summary of the Calculated ADR, AEDE, and ELCR of the Following Network Providers

	ADR (G y/s)	AEDE(S v/y)	ELCR(Sv-1)
ARTEL	0.000091	4.0176864×10^{-3}	$1.40619024 \times 10^{-3}$
ETISALAT	0.000195333	$8.624030083 \times 10^{-3}$	$3.018410529 \times 10^{-3}$
GLOBACOM	0.000488333	$2.156009728 \times 10^{-3}$	$7.546034049 \times 10^{-3}$
MTN	0.421352	$1860.285934 \times 10^{-3}$	$6511.000769 \times 10^{-3}$

Figure 1. AIRTEL mast with ID 047

Figure 2. ETISALAT mast with ID 0154

Figure 3. GLO mast with ID KAD 060

Figure 4. MTN mast with ID 0160

Conclusion

In this research work, the maximum power density value of each service provider mast was compared with the standard exposure limit given

by ICNIRP (4.5 W/m^2), FCC, and IEEE (6.05 W/m^2). The result shows that the values of the power density obtained from this research work fall below the standard exposure limit. The

compared result also established that the exposure rate of the electromagnetic beams emanating from telecommunication service providers masts (AIRTEL, ETISALAT, GLO, and MTN) causes hazardous health effects; apparently, the population who reside within the vicinity of such telecommunication masts are not safe from electromagnetic forces and ionizing radiation emanations; also, the calculated absorbed dose rates arising from the BIR levels of the masts and the annual effective radiation doses at these rates may not constitute an immediate radiological health effect on the mast workers and the general public, but it will in the long run. The values for the cancer risks obtained in this work are far higher than the average value of 0.29×10^{-3} per sievert as recommended by UNSCEAR (2018) and Audu *et al.*, (2019), which implies that people who live or work close to the base stations and who spend a long time there have the potential of developing cancer from the ages of 65 years and above. Although the studied base stations may not constitute an immediate risk both to human health and the environment, the result of this shows they will certainly do so in the long term (65 years and above). It is concluded that sitting on a telecommunication mast within 500 m in a residential area is not safe for the general public.

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